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GRACE MANUSCRIPT PROPOSAL

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PROPOSED TITLE

Global Responses of Airborne Grass Pollen to Climate Change (GRACE): C4 Grasses Drive Global Spatiotemporal Diversity and Airborne Poaceae Pollen Season Characteristics in Response to Climate Change

PROPOSED JOURNAL

Lancet Planetary Health

PROPOSED SUBMISSION DATE

February 2027

BACKGROUND

Grasses are the major and most important outdoor source of aeroallergens covering up to 43% of the Earth's land surface ([Stromberg et al., 2011](#)). With over 11,000 species ([Soreng et al., 2022](#)), different ecophysiology related to photosynthesis enable differential adaptation of grasses to diverse ecological niches ([Taylor et al., 2009](#)). Under elevated CO₂ and warming, the combined effects of climate change, biomass production increases more in warm-season (C4) than in cool-season (C3) grasses, especially when soil moisture is most limiting ([Morgan et al., 2021](#)). There is a wide range of dynamics in grass (Poaceae) pollen season, which likely reflects grass diversity ([Lo et al., 2019](#); [Davies et al., 2021](#)). In southeastern Australia, the ratio of C3 to C4 grasses increased with time related to warm season to cold season rainfall ratios ([Xie et al., 2022](#)). There has also been an increase by three-fold in grass season loads in subtropical Brisbane ([Addison-Smith et al., 2021](#)), where eDNA records demonstrate dominance of C4 species ([Campbell et al., 2023](#); [Van Haften et al., 2024](#)). However, previous studies have not detected change in seasonality and load of Poaceae pollen with climate change ([Ziello et al., 2012](#); [Ziska et al., 2019](#); [Anderegg et al., 2021](#)). This may be due to lumping C3 and C4 grasses together and limited focus on contribution of C4 in previous studies. Modelling also suggests that air temperature and precipitation might differentially affect net pollen production for C3 and C4 grasses ([Zhang and Steiner, 2022](#)). Not accounting for grass diversity may have previously masked the ability to discern changes in Poaceae pollen load and seasonality over time and in relation to climate change effects.

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PROPOSED AIMS

- To investigate **how local environmental conditions**, such as climate class, air temperature, solar radiation, humidity, precipitation and grass cover, **influence spatial and intra-annual distributions in grass diversity** (C3 versus C4 grasses) **globally**.
- To investigate **whether sites rich in C4 grasses exhibit different airborne Poaceae pollen season characteristics compared to C3-rich sites**.
- To investigate **whether airborne Poaceae pollen in C4-rich sites have different response to C3-rich-sites to air temperature and CO₂, as proxy for climate change**.

HYPOTHESES

- Spatial distributions of C3 and C4 grasses, and intra-annual variations in grass flowering influence airborne Poaceae pollen season characteristics and are related to environmental conditions globally.
- Locations with higher C4/C3 grass ratios are associated with longer airborne Poaceae pollen seasons.
- Airborne Poaceae pollen in C4-rich sites more prominently have changed due to climate change than C3-rich sites.

PROPOSED DATA SOURCES

- **Poaceae observation records** within 50km of a site as an indication of grass diversity and timing of flowering (grass diversity detected in observation records was related to diversity discovered in eDNA records ([Van Haeften et al., 2024](#))) will be obtained from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (**GBIF**).
- **Airborne Poaceae and total pollen daily concentration records** will be obtained from **pollen monitoring sites around the globe**.
- **Meteorological and climate data** (local air temperature, solar radiation, humidity, precipitation and atmospheric CO₂) for each pollen monitoring site will be obtained from the **ERA5** reanalysis dataset.
- **Land cover data** (% grass cover) will be obtained from the ESA's **World Cover**.

PROPOSED APPROACH AND DESIGN

Include sites that monitor pollen around the globe and ensure representation off all continents, range of latitudes and important Koppen climate classes.

Please see “[site_inclusion_framework_v1.0.pdf](#)”.

Use Poaceae observation records for each site to:

- Identify proportion of subfamilies (assigned based on genus; [Home - Taxonomy - NCBI](#)) and map them spatially and by month of a year

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- Identify proportion of C4 and C3 grasses (assigned based on genus; [Grass genera of the world - contents](#)) and map them spatially and by month of a year
- Examine proportion of C4 and C3 grasses spatially and intra-annually, in relation to a) airborne Poaceae pollen season length, start, peak and end, b) Koppen climate classes, c) latitude, d) air temperature, solar radiation, humidity and precipitation, and e) grass cover.
- Examine change in airborne Poaceae pollen peaks over time for C4 or C3-rich locations in relation to a) grass pollen season length; start, peak and end, b) Koppen climate classes, c) latitude, d) air temperature, solar radiation, humidity and precipitation, and e) grass cover.
- Look at changes in airborne Poaceae pollen load and seasonality in C3 versus C4 peaks in relation to CO₂ and warming (air temperature increase).

EXPECTED KEY OUTCOMES

- C4/C3 ratio indicates patterns of spatial and intra-annual grass diversity globally and there are different responses to environmental conditions for C3 versus C4-rich sites.
- C4-rich sites have prolonged airborne Poaceae pollen season
- C4-rich sites more prominently have changed due to climate change than C3-rich sites

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